

IN VITRO EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTS OF DIFFERENT EXTRACTS OF *Asparagus verticillatus* L. ON ACETYLCHOLINESTERASE ENZYME ACTIVITY

Keywords

Asparagus verticillatus,

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ABSTRACT

Acetylcholinesterase is one of the key enzymes responsible for the hydrolysis of acetylcholine at cholinergic synapses. Inhibition of AChE activity may contribute to an increase in acetylcholine levels in the synaptic cleft and to the enhancement of cholinergic neurotransmission. Therefore, AChE inhibitors are considered important pharmacological targets, particularly in the symptomatic treatment of neurodegenerative diseases such as Alzheimer's disease. In recent years, the effects of plant-derived secondary metabolites on AChE activity have been extensively investigated, and flavonoids, phenolic compounds, alkaloids, saponins, and terpenoids have been evaluated as potential natural inhibitor candidates. In this study, the effects of methanol, aqueous, and chloroform extracts obtained from *Asparagus verticillatus* L. on acetylcholinesterase enzyme activity were investigated under in vitro conditions. Plant samples were collected from the Ballica Village region of Koyulhisar district, Sivas province, and AChE activity was evaluated using the Ellman spectrophotometric method. The findings showed that the effects of the extracts on AChE activity varied depending on the extraction solvent used. While the methanol extract showed a slight tendency to increase AChE activity in a concentration-dependent manner, the aqueous and chloroform extracts demonstrated a limited tendency to reduce enzyme activity. These results suggest that the effects of *A. verticillatus* extracts on AChE may be associated with differences in the phytochemical compounds extracted depending on the solvent type. However, the limited level of the observed effect indicates that the AChE inhibition potential of this species should be further supported by detailed phytochemical analyses, different extraction methods, and studies at the level of isolated compounds.

INTRODUCTION

Acetylcholinesterase (AChE; EC 3.1.1.7) is one of the key enzymes that mediates the rapid hydrolysis of acetylcholine at cholinergic synapses and plays a critical role in the termination of synaptic transmission. Pharmacological inhibition of AChE activity may enhance cholinergic neurotransmission by allowing acetylcholine to remain in the synaptic cleft for a longer period. This mechanism forms the basis of current therapeutic approaches used in certain neurodegenerative diseases, particularly Alzheimer's disease. Therefore, AChE inhibitors are regarded as an important therapeutic class in the symptomatic treatment of Alzheimer's disease.^{1,2,3}

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The investigation of plant-derived AChE inhibitors has gained increasing importance due to both their traditional medicinal uses and the structural diversity offered by natural product chemistry. Numerous studies have reported that plants may represent a rich source of AChE inhibitors and that many phytochemical compounds can exert inhibitory effects on this enzyme². Similarly, plants traditionally used for cognitive disorders have been reported to be noteworthy in terms of their anti-cholinesterase, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory effects⁴. Medicinal plants possess a biologically important diversity of compounds due to the secondary metabolites they contain, such as alkaloids, flavonoids, phenolic acids, terpenoids, and saponins. Several studies have demonstrated that a considerable proportion of these phytochemical compounds exhibit neuroprotective effects and inhibitory activity against cholinesterase enzymes^{4,5}. Compared with synthetic drugs, plant-derived compounds are considered promising candidates in the management of neurodegenerative diseases owing to their potential for lower toxicity, better biological compatibility, and capacity to act through multiple pharmacological mechanisms.

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The genus *Asparagus* belongs to the family Asparagaceae and includes numerous species distributed worldwide, many of which have long been used in traditional medicine for the treatment of various diseases. Steroidal saponins, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, polysaccharides, and various bioactive metabolites have been identified in species belonging to this genus. Studies conducted on *Asparagus* roots and other plant parts have shown that these plants may possess antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, hypolipidemic, and potential neuroprotective effects⁶. In addition, a study on *Asparagus racemosus* demonstrated that the methanol extract of this species, in particular, acts as a non-selective competitive inhibitor of both cholinesterase and monoamine oxidase enzymes⁷. The antioxidant capacity of *Asparagus* extracts, associated with their phenolic/flavonoid content, may contribute to neuroprotective effects by reducing oxidative stress, which plays a role in the progression of neurodegenerative diseases^{8,9,10}. These findings indicate that *Asparagus* species are worthy of investigation in terms of their pharmacological effects related to the cholinergic system.

Asparagus verticillatus L. is a species that occurs naturally in the flora of Türkiye; however, its effects on AChE activity have been investigated only to a limited extent. Therefore, the aim of this study was to evaluate the effects of methanol, aqueous, and chloroform extracts obtained from *A. verticillatus* L. on AChE enzyme activity under in vitro conditions and to discuss, in light of preliminary findings, whether this species may be considered a potential candidate as a natural AChE inhibitor.

Collection of Plant Materials and Preparation of Plant Extracts

The *Asparagus verticillatus* L. specimens used in the study were collected from the Ballica Village region of Koyulhisar district, Sivas province, at the coordinates 40°25'38" N and 38°06'49" E. After being transported to the laboratory, the plant material was dried under appropriate conditions and prepared for extraction procedures. Species identification of the plant material was performed by Assoc. Prof. Dr. Hülya Özpınar, a faculty member of the Department of Pharmaceutical Botany, Faculty of Pharmacy, Sivas Cumhuriyet University.

Methanol, aqueous, and chloroform extracts were prepared from the plant material using solvents of different polarities.

The aerial parts of *Asparagus verticillatus* L. used in the study were first washed with tap water and then with distilled water, dried, and subsequently ground into powder. A total of 50 g of the powdered sample was taken, 150 mL of methanol was added, and the mixture was left for maceration in a shaker at room temperature for 48 hours. After two days, the samples were filtered through filter paper, and methanol was added again to the remaining plant material, followed by maceration for an additional two days¹¹.

After this procedure was repeated several times, the filtrates were combined in a single container, and the solvent in the filtrate was removed under reduced pressure at 40 °C using a rotary evaporator (Heidolph Hei-VAP Precision, Germany). After the obtained extract was completely dried, all samples were stored at -20 °C until analysis. The same procedures were repeated using water and chloroform as solvents.

Acetylcholinesterase Inhibition Assay

Acetylcholinesterase inhibitory activity was determined using the spectrophotometric method developed by Ellman et al. (1961). Briefly, the reaction mixture consisted of 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 8.0), DTNB (5,5'-dithiobis-(2-nitrobenzoic acid)), acetylthiocholine iodide as the substrate, enzyme solution, and *Asparagus verticillatus* L. extracts at different concentrations. The increase in absorbance resulting from the formation of 5-thio-2-nitrobenzoate was measured at a wavelength of 412 nm using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer¹².

RESULTS

The effects of aqueous, methanol, and chloroform extracts of the asparagus plant on acetylcholinesterase enzyme activity were investigated spectrophotometrically using the Ellman method. Based on the obtained data, percentage activity-inhibitor concentration graphs of the asparagus extracts were plotted and are presented in Figure 1.

In this study, the effects of methanol, aqueous, and chloroform extracts obtained from *A. verticillatus* L. on AChE activity were evaluated. The resulting graphs revealed different trends in enzyme activity depending on the type of extract.

Figure 1. % Activity - inhibitor concentration graphs of the *Asparagus verticillatus* L. extracts

In the methanol extract, a slight increasing trend in AChE activity was observed depending on the increasing concentrations. This finding suggests that the methanol extract did not exert a pronounced inhibitory effect on AChE within the tested concentration range. On the contrary, the possibility that certain components extracted with methanol may have a protective or slightly enhancing effect on enzyme activity should be considered.

In the aqueous extract, a limited decreasing trend in AChE activity was detected. This result suggests that polar components may exert a weak inhibitory effect on AChE. However, the low level of this effect and the limited graphical fit values are not sufficient to indicate strong inhibitory activity.

In the chloroform extract, a slight decreasing trend in AChE activity was observed, similar to that seen with the aqueous extract. Considering that the chloroform extract may contain relatively nonpolar compounds, it can be suggested that some phytochemicals present in this fraction may have modulated AChE activity to a limited extent. However, the current findings are far from demonstrating that the chloroform extract is a strong AChE inhibitor. Overall, the findings showed that the effects of *A. verticillatus* extracts on AChE activity varied depending on the solvent used.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In this study, the effects of methanol, aqueous, and chloroform extracts of *A. verticillatus* L. on acetylcholinesterase (AChE) enzyme activity were investigated. AChE inhibition is an important pharmacological mechanism in relation to Alzheimer's disease and other disorders of the cholinergic system. Although currently available clinical AChE inhibitors may provide symptomatic benefits, the search for new and safer natural inhibitor candidates remains highly relevant^{1,3}. The obtained results showed that the biological activities of the extracts varied depending on the extraction solvent used. This suggests that there are differences in the phytochemical compositions of the extracts. Among the tested extracts, the methanol extract was found to show a tendency to increase AChE activity in a concentration-dependent manner. This finding indicates that the compounds extracted with methanol may not possess pronounced inhibitory activity against AChE. It is thought that some compounds present in the methanolic

fraction may interact with the enzyme and preserve, or slightly enhance, its catalytic activity. Methanol is known to effectively extract phenolic compounds, flavonoids, and certain saponins from *Asparagus* species; however, not all phenolic compounds exhibit cholinesterase inhibitory properties.

The effects of plant extracts on AChE may vary depending on the extraction solvent and the phytochemical groups present in the extract composition. The presence of various bioactive constituents, such as steroidal saponins, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, and polysaccharides, has been reported in *Asparagus* species⁶. While some of these compound groups may exhibit antioxidant and neuroprotective effects, others may directly contribute to AChE inhibition. However, a high antioxidant potential of any plant does not necessarily mean that it is a strong AChE inhibitor.

The increasing trend in AChE activity observed in the methanol extract suggests that the extract does not possess inhibitory properties. Methanol can extract numerous polar to semi-polar compounds, such as phenolic compounds and flavonoids. Although flavonoids have been reported to act as AChE inhibitors, it is known that this effect depends on the structure of the compound, its hydroxylation pattern, glycosylation status, and mode of interaction with the enzyme¹³. Therefore, it is possible that the compounds present in the methanol extract may have exhibited a protective effect on enzyme activity or influenced the assay system, rather than inhibiting AChE.

The slight decrease in activity observed in the aqueous and chloroform extracts suggests that these fractions may contain components capable of suppressing AChE activity to a limited extent. However, the weak nature of this effect may be associated with the low concentration of active compounds, the complex structure of the extract, antagonistic interactions between components, or the inadequacy of the concentration range used. The reported inhibitory effects of *Asparagus racemosus* on enzymes involved in acetylcholine and monoamine metabolism support the idea that the genus *Asparagus* is worthy of investigation in terms of pharmacological effects related to the cholinergic system⁷. However, these findings cannot be directly generalized from one species to another, because the phytochemical profile may vary considerably depending on the species, locality, plant part, harvest time, and extraction conditions.

The shoots of *A. verticillatus* L. are consumed as food in many countries where the species grows naturally, while its seeds are prepared as an infusion and consumed as a beverage^{14,15,16}. This study represents a preliminary investigation evaluating the effects of *A. verticillatus* L. on AChE activity. The findings indicate that there is a limited tendency toward inhibition, particularly in the aqueous and chloroform extracts; however, more comprehensive experimental validation is needed to support any claim of strong AChE inhibitory activity. Rather than proving that *A. verticillatus* L. is a potent natural AChE inhibitor, the present results demonstrate that the solvent-dependent enzyme-modulating potential of this species should be further investigated in future studies.

Conflicts of Interest Statement

There are no potential conflicts of interest.

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No

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